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D2.5 - Provision of a Workflow Environment at BioExcel portal

WP2: Convergence of HPC/HPDA and Improved Usability

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Executive Summary

The deliverable presents the work to provide execution environments for workflows developed within the BioExcel 2 period.

The first section introduces the concept of workflow environments in the BioExcel Project, providing the context of the work done in the previous BioExcel 1 grant period and presents the current ecosystem around the BioExcel Cloud Portal.

The second section presents the Cloud Portal in more detail together with VM-based environments for workflows that are available in the portal. Different flavours of virtual machines (VMs) are presented, including BioExcel 1 pre-built VMs and dynamically built machines for Common Workflow language (CWL) and Jupyter Notebook execution.

Finally, the third section presents the newest type of workflow infrastructure in the form of the Binder installation and its container-based notebook servers.

This deliverable concentrates on execution environments for workflows and as such, does not describe the workflows themselves. All demonstration workflows added to the Portal during BioExcel 2 have been previously and extensively described in Deliverable 2.3.

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1 Workflow Environments in BioExcel

1.1 Context

With the amount of scientific data growing dramatically in recent years and the need for computational resources it generates, there has been an increased interest from the scientific community in cloud computing. Not only does the cloud promise to solve the scalability issue by providing potentially large resources on demand, but it also promotes reproducibility by requiring portable packaging of the code, so that it is able to run anywhere. However, the adoption of cloud computing is often affected by the lack of technical expertise among scientific users.

The EBI Cloud Portal (ECP) [[The public installation](#)] [[Read the docs](#)] [[API source code](#)] is a system that was originally designed to overcome this problem and provide a way for non-technical users to self-provision cloud infrastructure in the form of ready to use instances across different cloud providers. The audience was expected to be mostly scientific users using the portal to provision short-lived infrastructure primarily to run scientific pipelines.

However, the fact that the use cases in BioExcel are predominantly HPC-based and require large compute resources in combination with the relatively modest cloud resources available for the project resulted in the Cloud Portal being utilised during the BioExcel 1 period mostly for workshops and training sessions. The provisioned relatively light-weight environments were used for live experimentation with tools and demonstration workflows and not actually to execute scientific pipelines.

In BioExcel 2 this training use case is still valid and has been further explored, resulting in a number of improvements in the user experience during portal use for training events, and have been used for two successfully executed training sessions ([Reproducible analyses with Common Workflow Language, Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel Building Blocks](#)) to date. The additional ambition has always been to provide the portal to users in an unattended mode, so that they can experiment with the tools and workflows independently outside of a scheduled training event.

In the BioExcel 1 period all training environments were based on installations of pre-built images. This approach - still justified in a number of cases, such as installation of complex systems, difficult to script, with licencing restrictions and likely to be prepared for a single event (see 2.3.1) - came with a number of drawbacks, including code duplication, the lack of maintainability and portability of the code. It became particularly apparent for the [demonstration workflows](#) of the BioBB library, which have been undergoing intensive development and changes. For those in BioExcel 2 we revisited the idea of building VMs dynamically. Resulting work to date has provided two new flavours of VM environments: CWL-based and [Jupyter](#)-based.

Finally, containerisation has started to gain prominence in the scientific computing community. In comparison with the VM approach, containers offer potentially better utilisation of an underlying infrastructure, shorter launch time, an in-built solution for

caching artifacts in the form of container registries and a standardised description of appliances in the form of Dockerfiles.

The BioExcel demonstration workflows are packaged as Jupyter Notebooks and compatible with the widely used mybinder.org [1] execution platform, which under the hood uses the Kubernetes container orchestration platform and runs user notebook servers as containers. The shared interest in mybinder.org platform among BioExcel WP 2 participants resulted in an idea to host a private instance of the BinderHub, available exclusively for users to experiment with BioExcel related workflows. The proof of concept went well by demonstrating that the self-hosted version offers almost identical user experience to mybinder.org and full compatibility with demonstration workflows. This led to the decision to permanently include the BinderHub instances in the ecosystem of the Cloud Portal. One of the instances has been successfully integrated with the BioExcel Portal and will serve as an environment for training sessions, whereas the other one will hopefully realise the ambition of having a workflow environment open to users outside of scheduled training events.

1.2 Ecosystem

The current ecosystem of the BioExcel Cloud Portal consists of the following applications (as presented in Figure 1):

- The BioExcel Cloud Portal, which integrates with
 - The Cloud Portal API - launches VMs
 - A BinderHub installation with JSON Web Token (JWT) authentication - launches Containers
 - External systems
 - Authentication, Authorisation and Profile Service (AAP) & Elixir Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI)
 - bio.tools [2] API
- A separate installation of BinderHub with Github authentication, which will be integrated with the Demonstration Tutorials Website - launches Containers

Figure 1 Applications comprising the BioExcel Cloud Portal

Execution environments for workflows available in the BioExcel Portal are listed in Table 1.

The demonstration workflows added to the Portal during BioExcel 2 have been extensively described in Deliverable 2.3.

No	Workflow name	Added to the Portal (BioExcel 1 or 2)	Image based VM	CWL VM	Jupyter VM	Binder
1	NAFlex	1	x			
2	PyMDSetup	1	x			
3	Chromatin Dynamics	1	x			
4	Common Workflow Language with BioExcel Building Blocks	2		x		
5	Protein MD Setup	2			x	x
6	Automatic Ligand Parametrization	2			x	x
7	Protein Complex MD Setup	2			x	x
8	Mutation Free Energy Calculations	2			x	

Table 1 Workflow Environments installed in the BioExcel Portal

2 BioExcel Cloud Portal and Virtual Machine Environments

2.1 EBI Cloud Portal

The EBI Cloud Portal (ECP) which currently comprises one part of the back-end of the BioExcel cloud portal [[The public installation](#)] [[Read the docs](#)] [[API source code](#)], has been designed to provide a way for non-technical users to self-provision ready to use cloud VMs over the user-friendly web interface and without a steep learning curve. Such infrastructure was originally envisaged to be provisioned on demand - primarily to run scientific pipelines - and destroyed afterwards.

The EBI Cloud Portal uses the Infrastructure-as-Code approach (IaC). IaC is the management of infrastructure using descriptive coding language, most often declarative, and describing the desired state of the IT system, which promotes versioning, code reuse and automation. In the Portal the VMs are created and configured according to recipes stored as git repositories called *Applications*, the majority of which use a combination of [Terraform](#) and [Ansible](#) to describe cloud infrastructure and install required software. The portability between clouds is achieved by providing separate Terraform descriptions of cloud infrastructure within the same application.

Access to the cloud is handled in the Portal in the form of *Configurations*, which store cloud credentials provided by owners of the infrastructure bundled with parameters allowing for customised deployments.

Advanced end users can use their own application recipes and configure access to the cloud using their own credentials, but the majority of users are expected to benefit from the concept of *Sharing* and use applications provided by expert users and cloud access provided by administrators.

The EBI Cloud Portal (ECP) consists of a front-end written in [Angular](#) and a back-end being a [Spring Boot](#) API in Java. The execution of a deployment recipe can run as a separate process either in the same machine or inside a Docker container with the latter offering increased security.

The public instance of the EBI Cloud Portal is installed on top of EMBL-EBI [OpenStack](#) infrastructure called the [Embassy Cloud](#), but has no dependency on OpenStack and could have been installed elsewhere. Deployments can target any cloud provider that is supported by Terraform, but the majority of cloud deployments executed within the Portal target the same OpenStack installation, the Embassy Cloud.

Access to both the EBI Cloud Portal and the BioExcel Cloud portal described in the next section is guarded by JWT-based SSO provided by another EBI system called [AAP](#) in combination with the [Elixir AAI](#).

2.2 BioExcel Cloud Portal

Up to now, the only cloud infrastructure available for use as a deployment target for the Cloud Portal in the context of the BioExcel project has been the relatively modest infrastructure in the Embassy Cloud in EBI. Currently, the assigned tenancy capacity supports around 50 concurrently running VMs; each with 4 vCPUs/8 GB RAM. The possibility of users using their own infrastructure to deploy BioExcel VMs has not been actively tested to date, although further exploration of using other cloud environments (such as Fenix) rather than just Embassy Cloud is planned.

As a result, the modest infrastructure has not been sufficient for executing BioExcel scientific pipelines on full research datasets such as the ones needed for BioExcel-2 proposed use cases but is adequate to support demonstration and training where datasets are controlled and computation demands are less intensive. In theory up to 50 VMs are supported on current Embassy Cloud infrastructure. The training groups supported to date have had fewer participants, however, automated tests have been created and run successfully to simulate multiple VMs starting simultaneously. After the VMs are started they are independent from the portal and one another. The presented Bioexcel use cases (e.g. interactome, rational drug design) are ambitious projects that need an extremely high amount of computational resources at run-time, and they are therefore tackled using pre-exascale workflows in HPC supercomputers. These are extensively described elsewhere in deliverables D3.1 – ‘Use case work plans’- and D3.3 – ‘Use case reports’ and furthermore in D2.3 -First release of demonstration workflows.

Within the training context, the expected audience are users with little or no previous experience with the cloud or the Portal itself and who use the portal-built environments to experiment with BioExcel software and workflows on their own or during workshops and training events. These users range from wet-lab-based students with little coding experience to researchers with some previous experience of molecular dynamics. They are not expected to create their own applications directly and have been expected to use only shared infrastructure.

The decision was made during the BioExcel 1 period to simplify the user experience even further to reflect the expected use cases. The result was the BioExcel Cloud Portal [[The public installation](#)][[Frontend source code](#)], a separate front-end web application exclusively for the BioExcel use case, using the EBI Cloud Portal as its engine and [bio.tools](#) as an additional source of data. The BioExcel Cloud Portal offers a predefined portfolio of applications relevant in the BioExcel domain (sourced from the [bio.tools catalogue](#)) paired with configurations giving access to shared infrastructure where the resulting VMs can be deployed.

Additional support personnel are present at training events to help users resolve technical issues and observations are gathered on user interactions from this. In addition, we receive feedback forms from course participants. In the BioExcel 2 period some new features have been introduced to improve the user experience of running training events with the Portal even further, based on user feedback we received during previous events and issues that have been noticed during testing and training events.

Until recently the owner of infrastructure was the only user with the right to share access to infrastructure with other users by adding them to *Teams*. This meant that the owner (for EMBL-EBI cloud, one of EMBL-EBI personnel) had to get involved in authorising participants for each training event. We introduced a new role - *Team Managers*, a way to grant trainers the right to share infrastructure during the training events with training participants, thus obviating the need for local support for this step.

Additionally, the alternative way of logging in, not requiring an account in Elixir AAI was introduced as a way to mitigate the problems users had previously reported around establishing an account in Elixir AAI.

Finally, there is now a way for trainers and trainees to complete the entire training use-case within the BioExcel Cloud Portal front-end. Previously the step of initially requesting access to the training was done in the EBI Cloud Portal back-end.

2.3 Virtual Machine Environments

The infrastructure provisioned by the “classic” Cloud Portal is VM-based and a single deployment can consist of one or multiple VMs. In the next couple of chapters different types of VM environments built and published using the Portal have been described.

2.3.1 BioExcel 1 Machines

During the BioExcel 1 period the idea promoted by the Cloud Portal to describe software components as code was dropped and instead the cloud appliances were packaged as VM images. The preparation of VM images was done outside of the Portal by BioExcel partners experienced with the tools they wanted to demonstrate within the VMs, but not with the Cloud Portal application syntax. Additionally, often the tools installed within VMs were not published in a way that enabled easy programmatic installation.

As a result, simplified portal applications could be used that handled the infrastructure provision, but almost no code installation. In the end, three different flavours were used:

- An application uploading an image - most portable - this did not require the image to be present at a destination cloud provider, but unfortunately also with the biggest compatibility issues.
- An application launching an image already present at a cloud provider.
- An application as above, but additionally installing an NFS Client.

The finite list of applications resulted in an easy integration with [bio.tools](#), where each of the application types was assigned its own tag instructing the portal how to deploy the VM sourced from bio.tools.

The workflows packaged as these VMs are still available in the BioExcel Portal and include the following:

- **NAFlex**: a VM to explore Nucleic Acids flexibility through a wide range of analyses performed on a trajectory produced by a Molecular Dynamics simulation.
- **PyMDSetup**: a VM including the PyMDSetup Python package to set up systems to run molecular dynamics simulations.
- **Chromatin Dynamics**: a VM with all necessary tools to create coarse-grained, ‘beads-on-string’ like representations of a chromatin fiber from just a DNA sequence (linker), and the nucleosome positions, for generating a set of possible chromatin structure conformations.

The image-based VMs have a number of limitations:

- no easy way to maintain, update or modify the software within the image
- lack of insight of exactly what has been installed inside the VM
- a need to transfer the images between cloud providers
- potential incompatibility with target cloud providers
- code duplication (very similar images with small differences)

For these reasons the approach has been changed in BioExcel 2 and we returned to the idea of describing installations with Ansible. The advantages of this solution are as follows:

- the installation recipe is version-controlled source code that is easy to maintain and modify
- installation is done on top of standard OS images that reside at cloud provider sites and have been tested for compatibility
- recipes accept parameters for performing different installations with a single code-base.

We should note that there is still a place for image-based installations and the main advantages of using this approach is the short launch time and simplicity of preparing an installation. We still envisage the use of image-based environments in the Cloud Portal for complicated installations of - potentially - GUI software that would be otherwise difficult or impossible to script. Because of the problems with maintainability, such environments are likely to be prepared for a single training event only and not permanently published in the Portal. We know of a similar approach being successfully used by the EBI Training team.

2.3.2 Dynamic Environments

In BioExcel 2 the main goal of using the portal so far was to prepare environments for experimenting with [Demonstration Workflows](#). The workflows have been published primarily as [Jupyter Notebooks](#) with very well defined dependencies in [Conda](#) and

alternatively as [CWL](#) workflows. The installation of both types of execution environments is easily scriptable and the code can be easily parameterized to accommodate the execution of different workflows with just one code base. This made them good candidates for the approach originally promoted by the portal - to describe software installation as code.

This has resulted in two new types of portal applications - a so-called CWL VM and a Jupyter VM. Each of them accepts parameters, which can be passed as a configuration, and which enable the building of different workflows with the same code.

The recipes work well with the fact that demonstration workflows have been under intensive development - the newest version of workflow software is installed during the VM build. Also, the problem of portability has been mitigated as the dynamic VMs only use standard cloud OS images as a base of installation and are highly portable. However, the time of deployment increased to around 10 minutes in both cases, which is almost the limit of acceptable time for training environment preparation. Currently, the portal has no in-built method of caching built images.

Finally, the integration with bio.tools has become more complex. We felt that it would be valuable to maintain the approach of annotating the bio.tools entries representing workflows with metadata telling the portal how to deploy them. We achieved this by placing information about the application (CWL or Jupyter to date, but allowing for potential new ones) and the configuration (i.e. which workflow and which cloud) in the bio.tools catalogue. From the Portal user perspective it works as expected, but the value of the metadata from the bio.tools user perspective is not high and does not have the same meaning as the image download URL used in the past. It is likely that the current integration with bio.tools will be revised in the course of the project.

2.3.2.1 CWL VM

[Common Workflow Language](#) (CWL)[3] is an open standard for describing scientific workflows that is becoming increasingly popular in the bioinformatics community. All BioExcel Building Blocks have a description in CWL and currently one [Demonstration Workflow](#) exists, showcasing how these descriptions can be used to build a complete CWL workflow. Creating CWL equivalents of more Demonstration Workflows has been planned in the roadmap and is currently in progress.

CWL can be executed on a number of compatible platforms. [Cwltool](#) is the reference implementation of CWL and possibly the easiest to install execution platform of CWL. The portability of workflows is achieved by using dependencies described as Docker containers, which eliminates the need to install any dependencies of the workflow in the execution environment.

The idea behind the CWL VM was to build an environment where users can experiment with CWL workflows - including the BioExcel CWL Demonstration Workflows, modify them and execute them.

The resulting Portal Application is a recipe [[Github](#)] that dynamically provisions a VM with [cwltool](#) and Docker installed and clones a configurable CWL demonstration workflow into the filesystem. Users access the VM via SSH and can experiment with the workflow via command line or using SSH integration in one of the IDEs (such as VSCode). Figure 2 below presents the user interactions, when deploying CWL VM and accessing it via terminal SSH client.

Figure 2 An example CWL VM deployment in the BioExcel Portal

CWL VM functionality was successfully explored in the recent BioExcel Virtual Training event: '[Reproducible analyses with CWL](#)'. CWL VMs were used as environments for hands-on exercises by participants. Each participant created their own VM using the portal.

2.3.2.2 Jupyter VM

The [Jupyter Notebook](#) project is an extension of the console-based approach to interactive computing providing a web-based application with which programmers can develop, document, execute code, and share results. Notebooks have been widely

adopted in the educational context with tutorials combining executable code with documentation and visualisations of data.

The Jupyter Notebook consists of 2 elements as noted in the [Jupyter documentation](#):

- A web application, which gives a user a browser-based UI, where they can interact with the code and explore rich media output.
- Notebook documents which are code representation of all content visible in the web application, interleaving executable code with explanatory text and visualisation of resulting objects.

The fact that notebooks are code makes them suitable for version control and sharing.

The notebook document can be launched in a Jupyter web application running locally in a user's workstation. This approach requires that the user installs not only the notebook web application itself, but also all notebook document dependencies, such as libraries used within the notebook. This can be challenging at times for inexperienced users and even impossible for notebooks with particular technical requirements.

All Demonstration Workflows have been published as Jupyter Notebooks and thanks to excellent installation manuals their local installation is relatively easy, but still can discourage potential users from experimenting with workflows.

The possibility of dynamically building so-called Jupyter VMs in the Portal was our first attempt to prepare executable environments for notebooks, before we moved on to explore the BinderHub.

The resulting Portal Application [[Github](#)] provisions a VM in OpenStack, installs a single-user Jupyter server, installs dependencies of the notebook automatically and finally launches the notebook server and exposes it over the web with a randomly generated token. We followed the [guidelines in the official Jupyter documentation](#) of how to expose a single user Jupyter server remotely.

A user gets information in the Portal about the IP, where the notebook has been exposed and the password to access it. User interaction required to deploy and access a Jupyter VM has been presented in Figure 3.

Thanks to the fact that all Jupyter-based Demonstration Workflows have a standardised way of installation, only one configurable recipe was enough to install four different demonstration workflows to date. (see section 1.2, Table 1).

The additional dependency on Docker of the workflow [Mutation Free Energy Calculations](#) was accommodated by including an optional Docker installation task in the recipe. The workflow itself has been previously described in deliverables D2.2 and D2.3.

The Jupyter-based VMs are an alternative to the Binder approach described below and give a similar user experience, once first accessed. However, the launch time is much longer than for the Binder version, as there is no caching solution currently in the

Portal whereas the Binder benefits from cached Docker images. Also, opening the Jupyter VM notebook requires typing the IP in the browser URL bar and the secret to the notebook login page, so is more complicated than just clicking the button to launch the Binder version. Additionally, although single user servers on public interface are recognised in the [official Jupyter documentation](#) and [publications](#) and we followed the official guidelines with some work still needed around handling the password, the topic of security is better investigated and documented for JupyterHub (the backend of Binder) with in-built support for Single Sign On.

Jupyter VMs might still show their advantage over Binder in some instances. The Binder executes notebooks inside Docker containers, and hence notebooks which themselves require Docker access are not supported. Jupyter VMs, however, support workflows with an intrinsic Docker requirement. In addition, we have noticed that some tools, such as Gromacs, do not perform optimally when multiple instances run on the same instance (machine) in different containers.

The better isolation of execution environments achieved by Jupyter running them as separate VMs in this case results in improved performance.

Figure 3 An example deployment of a Jupyter VM

2.4 Prospects

The EBI Cloud Portal was designed with the ambitious goal of allowing users with little to no knowledge of IT management to easily self-provision the infrastructure they require to run scientific pipelines. Although the Portal has also been used

successfully in several other projects such as [PheNoMenal](#) it has not been heavily used elsewhere due to several inherent limitations. Firstly, the format of Portal Applications is arbitrary and hence potential authors need to learn it first before they can write new ones. This in turn results in the lack of reusable Applications for users. From the scientific users' perspective, the Portal has not really addressed the dual areas of input data access and storing results and this makes the Portal difficult to use directly for running real-life scientific pipelines on complex datasets. Finally, the shift of interest of scientists and developers over time from using VMs towards containers makes the original idea behind the portal less appealing.

However, in BioExcel, the Cloud Portal has found its niche as a system provisioning live environments for training and workshops. We acknowledge that the Portal is not going to be able to compete with dedicated established training platforms, but it does have the advantage of being open source and relatively uncomplicated to install and maintain. We see it as a complementary solution to the later adopted Binder, everywhere where an alternative user interface to Jupyter needs to be used or where Binder shows its limitations - for instance workflows with an intrinsic Docker requirement, not supported in the Binder or cases with insufficient isolation of workloads.

It is unlikely that the "classic" Portal is going to be offered to users to experiment independently with workflows outside of the training events. This would require the introduction of solutions facilitating 'fair sharing' of the infrastructure to ensure limited resources are used effectively. Such solutions including automatic session culling and limiting the number of concurrent sessions per user have already been implemented in the Binder and this is why the Binder will be the basis of the open access "BioExcel Portal".

The remaining area of exploration planned around the Portal is further investigation of the potential for using other cloud environments than just OpenStack. This has already been implemented in the Portal and presented as a Proof-of-Concept (for example using Amazon Web Services and Google Cloud), but rarely used in practice.

3 Containers and the Binder

3.1 Motivation

As discussed previously, BioExcel 2 Demonstration Workflows (see Table 1, section 1.2) have been published as Jupyter Notebooks and at times the requirement for local installation discourages potential users from testing the workflows.

Another alternative to local installation of notebooks and the previously discussed exclusive [remote notebook server](#) approach is the [JupyterHub](#) project, where notebooks are executed in a remote shared environment which is maintained by the JupyterHub server administrators. End users do not need to install anything locally and can interact with remote notebooks as usual using the web browser.

During the course of BioExcel2 a great improvement in accessibility of Demonstration Workflows has been made by integrating them with the new and promising platform [mybinder.org](#), which is a free-to-use cloud system extending JupyterHub that enables execution of notebooks shared as git repositories.

From a notebook developer perspective there is not much overhead needed to make a notebook compatible with mybinder.org. In most cases, simply following the standard conventions of describing dependencies in Python is enough to make a notebook Binder ready, but developers can take full control by writing custom Dockerfiles. Then integrating the notebook with mybinder.org is just a matter of placing a launch link next to the notebook code, usually as a GitHub badge. The user then only needs to click the badge to be taken to mybinder.org. If the notebook has not been launched before, the environment build process happens first and finally the user is presented with the usual notebook interface in the browser.

However, mybinder.org is publicly available and overloaded at times. Because binder is powered by an open source project with [well-documented local installations in other organisations](#) and is Kubernetes-based and therefore in the scope of current EMBL-EBI projects and of interest to BioExcel, made it an interesting proposition. Hence an attempt was made to install it locally and make it available exclusively for BioExcel Demonstration Workflows. The proof-of- concept installation and testing went sufficiently well to permanently include binder instances in the ecosystem of the Cloud Portal.

The private Binder instance is a promising platform for running events and so far the first remote interactive workshop - [Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel Building Blocks](#) – has utilised the Binder successfully.

3.2 Architecture and Installation

The [BinderHub](#) builds on top of the [Kubernetes](#)-based [Zero to JupyterHub installation](#). The installation process relies on [Helm](#). Single user notebooks run as

containers, so do the hub and the binder applications themselves. The notebook container images are built dynamically, based on well-structured notebook dependencies sourced from a public git repository.

The BinderHub uses [repo2docker](#) for that purpose. Repo2docker scans repositories for particular [configuration files](#) which are de-facto standards of defining dependencies for Python projects, such as: *environment.yml* for Conda, *Pipfile*, *requirements.txt*, and *setup.py* and builds a Docker image based on found dependencies. Alternatively, authors of repositories can supply repo2docker with a complete *Dockerfile*, which will be used instead.

The built images are stored in an image repository such as DockerHub. The build process only happens when BinderHub cannot find an already built image for a given repository version, which also means that images are built again after new commits in the repository.

The installation of the private BinderHub instance turned out to be relatively easy, especially as we could benefit from a preinstalled Kubernetes cluster. There were almost no required customisations for unauthenticated installation and the hugest problem was a required, not straightforward integration with an image repository, which failed for Gitlab and finally worked for DockerHub.

The Demonstration Workflows that have been compatible with mybinder (see Table 1, section 1.2) proved to be compatible with our private installation of the BinderHub.

3.3 Customisations

There were three main areas where the current BinderHub solution proved insufficient for our requirements and there was a need to extend the code. Fortunately, BinderHub offers many extension points and is easily customisable and the resulting solution only needed additional code patching in one area.

UI customisation: The default user interface of a newly installed BinderHub is almost identical to mybinder.org. It contains references to mybinder.org that might be misleading for a private instance. Following the [official guidelines](#) we prepared a customised user interface of the BinderHub that will be used in the instance with Github authentication, where the users are expected to experiment without supervision and need clear messages. The initial customisation was performed to focus the interface on features in use for our use cases. The original landing page for the Binder with required authentication was one single “Log in” button on a blank page with no accompanying text. We wanted the page to resemble the unauthenticated Binder landing page. We also removed all references of how to link a repository to the binder, as we want users to experiment with BioExcel notebooks rather than integrating their own repositories. The customisations are stored as code [[EBI Gitlab](#)] to ease maintenance and updating. More formal useability research will be undertaken in future and used to focus a second phase of improvement. However, we note that

Binder itself is a third-party software product and this may limit the type of customisation possible.

Authentication: We started to investigate authentication in the Binder with the idea of integrating the Binder with the Portal. We wanted the Binder to use the same JWT-based mechanism together with group-based permissions that have been used in the Portal. Such an option was not available among the authenticators offered in the Binder. Fortunately, we discovered a suitable community project JWTAuthenticator [[Github](#)]. Apart from authenticating the user, the requirement was to be able to grant access only to users whose tokens contain a particular claim, which represents a group membership. We extended the code to meet this requirement [[Github](#)].

Stopping the previous server: Enabling authentication in BinderHub activates the restriction on the number of active servers a user can simultaneously run. However, when a user tries to launch another notebook server once over the limit, the default implementation only informs a user about the limit but does not enable stopping a previous notebook server easily. We were keen on enforcing the restriction of one notebook server per user at a time but wanted also to keep it user-friendly. We therefore tried to either stop the previous server on launch or expose a way of stopping the existing server from the launch page. Of these two options, stop-on-launch turned out to be easier, but unfortunately no existing extension points in the binder code allowed us to achieve it by configuration. The result is a fragment of code using a technique called 'monkey patching' in Python that we managed to include in the configuration. The code is not currently public, but together with all our BinderHub installation options and extensions will be published in the near future. The feature has been actively used in one training event to date and worked well where users started one notebook and then went on to work with another one. More investigations will be needed to understand the use of this feature by users of the 'Binder for biobb' offering (where users explore demonstration workflows in their own time) and this will be a focus for future work.

3.4 Infrastructure, Installations and User Experience

Currently, two separate installations of BinderHub have been installed within the cloud infrastructure of EMBL-EBI in the OpenStack instance called the Embassy Cloud.

The first instance (<http://binder.tsi.ebi.ac.uk/>) is not directly available for the user under its URL; instead, it is accessible for the end user via the BioExcel Cloud Portal as an alternative offering to the VM deployments (Figure 4). The instance is secured by the custom JWT Authenticator, which allowed us to reuse the authentication and authorisation infrastructure used by the Portal. The repositories available for being launched in this Binder instance are sourced from additional metadata stored in bio.tools [- the Binder link. In most cases the same workflows are eligible to be

launched as Jupyter VMs, so the annotations for the Binder have been added next to annotations for the Cloud Portal in bio.tools.

The intended use of the instance is to run training and workshops where users are expected to interact with Jupyter Notebooks. The first event using the Binder is the recent [Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel Building Blocks](#).

The current infrastructure for this installation is a Kubernetes cluster with three master nodes and six worker nodes of 16 vCPUs and 32 GB RAM each.

Figure 4 Launching a notebook in the Binder in the BioExcel Portal

The motivation for the second instance of the Binder came from realising we cannot have both an instance that is openly available for the wide audience and which has sufficient guaranteed availability during the training sessions. We have decided to keep the training instance restricted and accessed by request only and publish another one. The second instance will soon be available publicly as <http://bioexcel-binder.tsi.ebi.ac.uk/>. Due to the relatively limited resources for the instance, the decision has been made not to make it public for anonymous users as mybinder.org does, but to require a lightweight authentication and also restrict the number of notebook servers available to a user to one at any given time. Elixir AAI has seemed not widely enough adopted to use it as an Identity Provider, so instead out of [available options](#) implemented in the BinderHub/JupyterHub project, we have selected Github. The reasoning behind Github was that a considerable number of the potential users of this BinderHub installation are already considering the use of the BioBB library, are interested in Open Source software and hence likely to already have had a Github account.

This instance is likely to benefit from the feature of culling inactive sessions and destroying running notebooks on logout, in order to promote fair access to resources for a bigger number of users. Also the customisation of the Binder unavailable in the original code base, which stops the previous notebook server for the user before launching a new one, was implemented mostly taking this use case into consideration.

The users are expected to discover the existence of this instance by visiting the [BioBB tutorials website](#). The user experience of discovery from this site has not yet been explored. The website will contain the links directly enabling the launching of respective repositories, similarly to how it now works with mybinder.org. The only difference in user experience will be the request to authenticate (Figure 5).

The infrastructure available currently for this instance is a Kubernetes cluster with three worker nodes of four vCPUs, 8 GB RAM each.

Figure 5 Launching an instance in an open-access Binder instance (not yet in production)

An interesting feature of a Jupyter Notebook discovered in the process of the Binder setup is a Terminal view (Figure 6). The user can access a console-like interface via the browser and execute command line methods in the same Python environment, where the notebook is running. This particular feature, together with the syntax-highlighting text editor also provided by Jupyter, was used extensively during the recent [BioBB virtual training](#) event. The event received positive feedback from the users regarding hands-on exercises performed in the Binder (although nobody

mentioned the platform in their feedback specifically). Feedback from further training events will be fed into ongoing development.

Figure 6 The Terminal view in a Demonstration Workflow Jupyter Notebook

3.5 Future Work

After almost a year of experiments and gaining experience with the BinderHub, we are confident that it will become a permanent addition to the BioExcel Portal and that it will prove its usefulness as a training and experimentation platform. Further training events using the Binder are planned but have not been finalised yet. Once we launch “The Binder for biobb” we will start logging and tracking its usage. While we have not yet performed formal user experience assessment of the Binder for biobb, this will be a target for future work.

Another area for future work is to further characterise the management of cpu and memory resources for processes running as Kubernetes pods, which is how Binder notebook servers are run. This becomes important when software run in the Binder uses multiple cores (e.g. GROMACS). More work is needed to investigate the full interplay between the Binder configuration options, Kubernetes CPU and RAM limits to ensure running software is presented with the ‘correct’ resource information for the pod rather than that of the whole compute node. The current implementation available in the Binder relies on Kubernetes throttling CPU time, which results in an ineffective execution.

From the perspective of the Cloud Portal implementers we are especially keen on the features the Binder solves that were not solved in the original Cloud Portal:

- The Cloud Portal promotes Infrastructure-as-Code approach, but the format of portal applications is arbitrary and potential adopters need to learn it. The Binder using repo2docker follows the standard practices of defining Python

dependencies and/or allows a user to define a standard Dockerfile - authors of binder compatible repositories do not need to learn new things.

- Similarly to the Cloud Portal, the environment in the Binder is built dynamically based on repository code, but unlike the Portal, the Binder handles caching by using an image repository (such as DockerHub). The build process is happening only when changes in the code have been detected and otherwise built images are used.

The launching process and access to the resulting environment appear much more user friendly with the Binder (so far based on the subjective impression of developers and practical experience of the users during the first live session). There has been a considerable effort concentrated on authentication and fair access to resources for users (measures to ensure that individual users cannot use all available resources), but we realise that the original implementation of authentication in BinderHub still needs to be improved and topics of data protection and security further explored. So far, authentication has followed standards such as OAuth2/OIDC, so that users can be identified and resources available to them limited. As this requires collecting and storing limited user data we performed GDPR compliance analysis and generated a suitable Data Privacy Notice. Users are also warned not to share sensitive data when using binder instances. However, currently logging out of BinderHub is not possible (user logs out only from JupyterHub). The need for additional SSO identity provider options in one installation - such as a choice to log in via Github or Google has been identified and will be investigated.

Data protection and security in general extend far beyond authentication and further work is required in this general area. Both the Portal and the Binder allow arbitrary code execution and so come with security implications – the code can be malicious and neither the Portal nor the Binder perform security analysis of the code. Security is improved by separating the arbitrary code execution from the application itself and other user processes (the deployment scripts for the portal and any code execution happening in the notebook), restricting the allowed codebases to analysed/approved ones (both Binder and portal allow whitelisting repositories and the portal allows whitelisting Applications allowed to run on particular infrastructure) and monitoring the behaviour to catch suspicious activity.

Mybinder.org put the bar high for [documentation](#) and - [publicly observable](#) - [monitoring infrastructure](#). The BioExcel Binder is going to follow the best practices in these areas.

4 Conclusions

The BioExcel Cloud Portal was used in the BioExcel 1 period as a way to provision environments for training events. This continues to be the most important use case in BioExcel 2 as well. A number of new features have been introduced to improve the training experience; the main use to date: ‘Team Managers’ role, ability to log in without an Elixir AAI account, ability to request team access directly in the BioExcel Portal.

The image based VMs introduced in BioExcel 1 are still available and a valid potential solution for complicated installations that do not need to be further maintained, such as a single training event. However, the approach to build VMs based on code description was reintroduced in BioExcel 2 and the resulting Jupyter VM recipe and CWL recipe are flexible enough to provision executable environments for the majority of BioExcel 2 Demonstration Workflows. CWL VM has been already used in a training event successfully.

Finally, the idea to install a private instance of BinderHub proved promising enough for the Binder installation to be integrated permanently with the BioExcel Cloud Portal and serve as an additional training infrastructure, already successfully used in a training event. An additional Binder instance will soon be available for the general public outside of training events with the expected patterns of use similar to mybinder.org. We plan to investigate user experience of using a binder instance in this way later in the project and use this to inform further developments.

5 References

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